

Review Article

Complex Regional Pain Syndrome: A Comprehensive Review of Current Understanding and Management Strategies

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Abstract

Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (CRPS) is a challenging clinical condition characterized by disproportionate and persistent pain accompanied by sensory, motor, and autonomic alterations. This review addresses current aspects of CRPS, including classification, pathophysiology, and therapeutic approaches. This intricate disease impacts patients' quality of life, affecting physical functions and psychosocial aspects. Diagnosis is primarily clinical, based on the Budapest Criteria. CRPS treatment requires a multidisciplinary and stepped approach, starting with conservative therapies such as pharmacotherapy, physiotherapy, and psychological interventions. In refractory cases, interventional techniques such as sympathetic system blocks, spinal cord stimulation, and surgical approaches may be considered. Treatment efficacy is closely linked to early diagnosis and timely intervention. Recent advances in understanding the underlying mechanisms of CRPS, including the role of the immune system and pro-inflammatory cytokines, have opened new perspectives for targeted therapies. Here, we reviewed the pivotal benefits of an individualized and multifaceted approach in CRPS management, aiming at the improvement of treatment strategies and clinical outcomes.

Keywords: complex regional pain syndrome; neuropathic pain, combined modality therapy, sympathetic block; pain pathophysiology

Introduction

Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (CRPS) is a debilitating systemic condition characterized by disproportionate and persistent pain, accompanied by sensory, motor, and autonomic alterations. This pathology, recognized as a systemic disease of clinical diagnosis, involves a complex interaction of inflammatory, immunological, neurogenic, genetic, and psychological factors [1,2].

The pathophysiology of CRPS is multifaceted, involving central and peripheral sensitization, neurochemical alterations, and autonomic dysfunction [3,4]. Recent studies have highlighted the role of pro-inflammatory cytokines and immune system activation in the pathogenesis of the disease [5,6].

CRPS impacts patients' quality of life substantially, affecting not only physical function but also psychosocial aspects [7]. Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment are crucial for improving prognosis, although CRPS management remains a clinical challenge [8]. This article aims to provide an updated and comprehensive review of CRPS, addressing its classification, pathophysiology, diagnosis, and current therapeutic strategies, emphasizing multimodal and interventional approaches. The intention is to give healthcare professionals a contemporary view of this condition, highlighting recent advances in understanding its mechanisms and available treatment options.

History

Over the years, CRPS had an interesting history dating back to the 16th century when Ambrosie Paré described clinical cases with signs and symp-

toms characteristic of this pathology after phlebotomy [2,7,9].

In the 19th century, there were significant advances in understanding this condition. In 1864, Silas Mitchell observed that patients with gunshot wounds presented signs and symptoms similar to what we now know as CRPS-II. A few years later, in 1872, the term "causalgia" was introduced to describe this syndrome [2,7,9].

With the new developments of the 20th century, the nomenclature and understanding of CRPS advanced substantially. In 1946, James A. Evans coined the term "Reflex Sympathetic Dystrophy" to describe a similar condition, which he suspected was mediated by sympathetic system dysfunction [2,7,9].

An important milestone occurred in 1994 when the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) officially adopted the term "Complex Regional Pain Syndrome" and proposed diagnostic criteria. In the same year, IASP classified CRPS into two subtypes: subtype I, previously known as "Reflex Sympathetic Dystrophy," which occurs in the absence of nerve injury, and subtype II, previously called "Causalgia," which develops after nerve trauma [2,7,9].

In 2007, a revision of the CRPS criteria was proposed, later revalidated in 2010. This revision, known as the "Budapest Criteria," defined four categories of symptoms: 1) sensory, 2) vasomotor, 3) sudomotor/edema, and 4) motor/trophic [10].

Currently, two subtypes of CRPS are clinically indistinguishable and can

be further classified as "warm or cold" and "sympathetically maintained or sympathetically independent" in most cases. This detailed classification allows for different approaches regarding the available treatment modalities for this complex condition [11].

Pain Classification

Pain manifestations involve both peripheral and central nervous systems. Regarding the source mechanisms, pain has been classified as nociceptive, neuroplastic, or nociplastic. It can also be classified as acute (physiological) or chronic [12].

Nociceptive pain results from actual tissue injury, somatic or visceral, with activation of primary nociceptive afferents (C and A α fibers), maintaining the integrity of sensory nerves. Neuropathic pain results from direct injury or disease affecting the somatosensory system subdivided into peripheral or central [12].

In 2014, the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) introduced the third classification as Nociplastic Pain, referring to pain that is not classified as Nociceptive or Neuropathic without evidence of tissue injury directly affecting the somatosensory system. Examples include Fibromyalgia, CRPS-I, and Irritable Bowel Syndrome [12].

In this context, CRPS-I has been classified as Nociplastic, and CRPS-II is considered Neuropathic due to the presence of prior neural injury in the clinical history. CRPS-II occurs in 5% of cases after injury or surgery, particularly of the limbs, with an incidence between 5-26/100,000 [13,14].

It is important to note that, in many cases, blocking the responsible sympathetic system may not result in pain relief or improvement of the clinical picture. CRPS-I, with no demonstrable neuropathic lesion, could be divided into a) Responsive to sympathetic blocks and b) Not responsive to sympathetic blocks. This distinction is crucial for understanding the complexity of the syndrome and its possible therapeutic approaches.

Pathophysiology

Peripheral nerve injuries can result in persistent pain that exceeds the average tissue healing time, indicating an active pathological process that can become chronic [15]. Complex Regional Pain Syndrome type II (CRPS-II) is an example of chronic neuropathic pain characterized by significant disorders in inflammatory and autonomic processes.

The pathophysiology of CRPS involves peripheral and central mechanisms, including central and peripheral sensitization, neurochemical alterations, psychological and genetic factors, and changes in autonomic, inflammatory, and possibly autoimmune systems [3,4]. Although it has been suggested that CRPS is an autoimmune disease, scientific evidence to date is limited [16].

Immune system activation is amplified and persistent in patients with CRPS [5]. This process initiates keratinocyte proliferation and the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-6, IL-1 β , and tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α) [6]. These cytokines trigger a cascade that results in histamine-induced vasodilation, causing the characteristic symptoms of the acute phase of CRPS: flushing, edema, pain, and increased temperature [3].

In the chronic phase, pro-inflammatory cytokines activate osteoblasts and osteoclasts, resulting in osteoporosis [17]. Studies have documented the presence of CD4+ and CD8+ lymphocytes, suggesting a partially T-lymphocyte-mediated response [18].

Neuropathic inflammation involves the activation of C nociceptive fibers, resulting in pain transmission to the spinal cord and β fferents towards the affected tissue through the release of substance P and calcitonin gene-re-

lated peptide (CGRP) [19]. This inflammatory process contributes to the allodynia and hyperalgesia observed in CRPS [20].

A decrease in A- α motor efferent fibers in the affected region has also been reported. In contrast, A- δ nociceptive fibers were spared, explaining the characteristic hyperalgesia and allodynia presentation [21]. Additionally, patients with CRPS showed an increase in CD39+, which acts as an inhibitor of T lymphocyte (Th17) differentiation [22].

In neuropathic pain, peripheral processes include mediator proliferation, changes in calcium channels, hyperpolarization in potassium channels, and neuronal and autonomic nervous system sprouting around nociceptive terminals.

Central Nervous System (CNS) alterations involve the activation of microglia, oligodendrocytes, and astrocytes, as well as an increase in the production of growth factors and neurotrophic factors, associated with loss of inhibitory pain control, resulting in hyperexcitability and maintenance of neuropathic pain [23].

Recent studies have also discussed the contribution of microglia's toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4) in the transition from acute pain to chronic pain disease [24].

Pathophysiology Pain Syndrome

CRPS treatment involves a multidisciplinary approach, including pharmacotherapy, physiotherapy, psychological and occupational therapy, and interventional techniques. Scientific evidence points to a progression in treatment, starting with conservative approaches and advancing to more complex interventions as needed [25].

The therapeutic process usually begins with conservative treatments, such as medications and physiotherapy. In cases of insufficient response, interventional techniques may be performed, including blocks for the neuropathic and autonomic components of pain. These interventions include sympathetic system blocks, dorsal ganglion blocks, plexus blocks, and sacral epidural blocks. Spinal cord stimulator implantation can be considered an advanced therapeutic option in refractory cases [26,27].

There is a consensus in the literature on the advantages of early treatment of CRPS [26,27]. The therapeutic approach should be individualized, with a progressive increase in the complexity of interventions, depending on the patient's clinical evolution [25].

Conservative Treatment

Pharmacological treatments have been considered more effective in the acute phase, but different approaches for subtypes I and II. The pathophysiology of CRPS-II includes initial nerve injury that leads to the neuropathic pain component present in this disease. Pharmacological treatments have been considered more effective in the acute phase, but different approaches for subtypes I and II [7,28,29].

For the management of neuropathic pain, several drugs are indicated, including gabapentin, pregabalin, antidepressants, opioids such as tramadol, and topical application of the local anesthetic lidocaine [30]. In subtype I, initial treatment may include steroids, bisphosphonates, ketamine, and dermatological creams, while in subtype II, the initial focus is on neuropathic injury [28,7,29].

Anti-inflammatory drugs have not proven significant efficacy in the treatment of CRPS. On the other hand, the short-term use of steroids, bisphosphonates, gabapentin, ketamine, and antioxidants such as Vitamin C has shown promising results [9,29]. Particularly, bisphosphonates have demonstrated efficacy in the treatment of CRPS-I [48].

In addition to pharmacotherapy, non-pharmacological approaches have been explored. Mirror therapy, where the patient looks at the healthy contralateral limb and tries to perform movements with the affected limb, observing the reflected movement in the unaffected area and laterality recognition, has shown positive results [9,49]. However, robust studies on using these approaches for CRPS-II are still scarce in the literature [31,49].

Interventional Treatment

When conservative treatment fails, the interventional approach becomes a pivotal therapeutic option [32]. Interventional treatment for CRPS should progress from less invasive techniques to more complex procedures, always considering the disease's pathophysiology and the patient's individual characteristics.

Sympathetic system blocks are frequently used, although results in the literature are contradictory [33]. When the response is adequate but short-lived, radiofrequency may be a valuable alternative. Detailed anatomical knowledge of the sympathetic system is crucial for effectively managing CRPS, considering the differences in innervation above and below the Diaphragm.

The sympathetic nervous system plays a crucial role in the pathophysiology and management of the CRPS. Its anatomical and functional organization is fundamental to understanding all interventional therapeutic approaches for this condition.

The sympathetic system diverges to innervate somatic and visceral nociceptive tissues, presenting a distinct organization above and below the Diaphragm, as follows:

Above the Diaphragm: the ipsilateral paravertebral thoracic sympathetic ganglia of T2 and T3 innervate both visceral and somatic tissues. The ipsilateral stellate ganglion is the main target for the upper limbs and cervical region. The thoracic and stellate sympathetic ganglia derive from sympathetic pathways originating from the lateral intermediolateral horn of T1 to T4. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the sympathetic system for visceral and somatic tissues above the diaphragm muscle showing the ipsilateral paravertebral thoracic sympathetic ganglia of T2 and T4 innervating both visceral and somatic tissues.

Below the Diaphragm: sympathetic innervation originates from fibers of the lateral intermediolateral horn of T5 to T12 (greater, lesser, and least splanchnic nerves); somatic nociceptive tissue is innervated by paravertebral ganglia, with concentration in the L3 lumbar sympathetic ganglion, while visceral nociceptive tissue is innervated by pre-vertebral plexuses (celiac, hypogastric, and their subdivisions) and by the Impar ganglion or Walter's ganglion. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the sympathetic system for visceral and somatic tissues below the diaphragm muscle showing the ipsilateral paravertebral ganglia of the lumbar sympathetic chain innervating the somatic tissues. Note that the prevertebral ganglia innervate the visceral tissue of this region.

The sympathetic system has trophic and pro-nociceptive functions in tissues. In CRPS, blocking sympathetic afference can indirectly relieve ischemic pain and interrupt nociceptive transmission from internal organs. This effect occurs because visceral nociceptive C and A δ afferent fibers physically pass within the sympathetic plexus before synapsing with the second pain neuron in the spinal cord. Therefore, a detailed understanding of the anatomy of the autonomic sympathetic nervous system is crucial for effectively managing CRPS. Comprehending those details allows an appropriate selection of targets for sympathetic blocks, considering the pain transmission pathways in CRPS, and thus developing more precise and effective therapeutic strategies.

For CRPS-II, due to neuropathic involvement, in addition to sympathetic blocks, blocks targeting the nociceptive fibers involved in the injury are indicated, such as plexus, dorsal ganglion, and sacral epidural blocks [34]. In refractory cases, spinal cord stimulator implantation may be considered. Other promising treatment options include naltrexone and botulinum toxin-A, especially when the motor component of the disease is predominant [9].

It is important to emphasize that, even during the interventional treatment phase, patients should maintain occupational therapy, including graded motor therapy and imagining movements in the affected area, to achieve better therapeutic success.

As a last resort, in cases of refractory CRPS-II, surgical approaches, such as resection with nerve grafting, may be considered [36].

Conclusion

CRPS continues to be a significant challenge for both patients and healthcare professionals. This literature review highlights the complexity of CRPS pathophysiology, involving intricate interactions between the nervous, immune, and endocrine systems.

Early and accurate diagnosis of CRPS is crucial for effective management. The Budapest Criteria provide a valuable framework for diagnosis, although the heterogeneity of clinical presentation may still hinder rapid identification of the syndrome.

CRPS treatment requires a multidisciplinary and individualized approach. Current evidence supports a treatment progression, starting with conservative measures such as pharmacotherapy and physical therapy and advancing to more complex interventions when necessary. The role of the sympathetic nervous system in CRPS is particularly notable, and interven-

tions targeting this system have shown promising results in many cases. Critical knowledge gaps still exist despite significant advances in understanding and treating CRPS. Future research should focus on elucidating the underlying molecular mechanisms of the syndrome, developing biomarkers for diagnosis and prognosis, and optimizing treatment strategies. Healthcare professionals must be aware of CRPS and its clinical manifestations to ensure early diagnosis and appropriate treatment. Continuous education and multidisciplinary collaboration are essential to improve outcomes for patients with this challenging condition.

Ultimately, successful management of CRPS requires a patient-centered approach, combining the best available scientific evidence with clinical experience and patient preferences. As our understanding of CRPS continues to evolve, we can expect the development of more effective and personalized treatment strategies in the future.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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